

A Comprehensive Review of the Quality of Drinking and Agricultural Water in the Gambia

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Abstract

Water pollution in The Gambia represents a significant environmental concern, particularly in urban areas and along riverbanks. This study aims to conduct a comprehensive assessment of the current state of water pollution in The Gambia and its implications for both drinking and irrigation water resources. Utilizing secondary data obtained from a variety of reputable sources, including official government websites of The Gambia and academic databases such as ScienceDirect, Scopus, Springer, ResearchGate, and Google Scholar, this research seeks to elucidate the primary status of potable and agricultural water resources within The Gambia. The Gambia River, along with its tributaries, rainwater, and borehole sources, constitutes a vital resource for agricultural practices. A significant portion of the population, particularly in urban centers, depends on the National Water and Electricity Company (NAWEC) for their drinking water supply. Numerous households have turned to domestic boreholes as a primary source of potable water and for agricultural applications, attributable to the heightened demand for water services from NAWEC and its inadequacy in providing comprehensive coverage across the nation. However, the utilization of these boreholes presents significant contamination risks, primarily due to insufficient routine disinfection protocols and inadequate monitoring by the Department of Water Resources. In 2018, The Gambia achieved significant progress in enhancing the quality of potable water, increasing access from 86% in 2010 to 90% of the population. However, it is noteworthy that only 34% of households have access to safely managed drinking water services.

Keywords: *water pollution, water quality, drinking water, irrigation, The Gambia.*

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Introduction

It is widely recognized that water is essential for human survival, ranking as one of the most crucial basic needs for all living entities (Postel, 2000); (Kılıç, 2021); (Kristanti et al., 2022). While water is vital for our existence, its contamination with pollutants can lead us to a painful demise. Research shows that urbanization and

population growth are adversely affecting waters and watersheds worldwide (Healey, 2014); (Sidabutar et al., 2017); (Mokaya et al., 2004). In developing nations like the Gambia, the presence of pathogenic microorganisms or various chemical pollutants in drinking water can result in severe diseases when consumed or used for bathing. Human activities pose significant threats to global water quality, with the situation

being particularly alarming in developing countries. Such activities continue to impact both drinking water and agricultural water quality (Akhtar et al., 2021). Numerous studies, especially in recent years, have highlighted the detrimental effects of human actions on the quality of drinking and agricultural water (Giri, 2021); (Wang et al., 2021); (Mishra, 2023).

While human impacts on water quality vary by region, many activities are globally similar. For instance, research by (Rashid & Romshoo, 2013) found that water quality worsened during the peak tourist and agricultural seasons from June to August in the Kashmir Himalayas. The findings indicated that total phosphorus, orthophosphate phosphorus, nitrate nitrogen, and ammoniacal nitrogen levels rose in July and August, whereas dissolved oxygen concentrations fell, leading to poorer water quality. The authors concluded that human activities, including the influx of tourists during peak times and the heavy use of fertilizers and pesticides in farming and gardening during the growing season, are key factors contributing to the declining water quality of the Lidder River in Kashmir Himalayas. During peak tourist seasons, increased human activities are recorded in this river catchment area, leading to further deterioration of water quality. (Kulk et al., 2021) support the connection between population growth and water quality decline, stating that anthropogenic pressures, such as agriculture, industry, and tourism, have adverse ecological and socioeconomic effects. These impact not only the achievement of goals outlined in SDG-14 but also those related to water quality (SDG-6) and health (SDG-3). In contrast, the authors revealed that water quality in Lake Vembanad improved during the lockdown period in April and May 2020, when human activities decreased. This underscores the need for strategies to mitigate human activity for the sustainable management of coastal ecosystems and water resources.

Similarly, a study conducted by (Sidabutar et al., 2017) on the raw water quality in Jakarta found that it does not comply with government standards owing to significant pollution from anthropogenic activities along the West Tarum Canal. Their findings indicated that primary

sources of pollution encompass domestic activities such as washing, cooking, and bathing, in addition to littering and the discharge of domestic wastewater into the river. As the population continues to increase, it becomes increasingly imperative for authorities to enforce regulations that mitigate behaviors detrimental to water quality. Moreover, authorities need to prioritize the establishment of wastewater treatment facilities for domestic discharges to alleviate the extent of water pollution. In a related analysis, (Mokaya et al., 2004) assessed stressor sources (e.g., factories and wastewater ponds) and the overall stream water quality of the Njoro River in Kenya, utilizing total phosphorus (TP), orthophosphate, ammonia-nitrogen, and nitrate-nitrogen as key parameters. They discovered that ammonia-nitrogen, TP, and orthophosphate were present in higher concentrations in the wastewater compared to the river water, while nitrate-nitrogen exhibited lower levels. Furthermore, they asserted that River Njoro experiences stress from nutrient influxes attributable to activities within its catchment area. As the population surrounding the river continues to expand, the nutrient load into the river is expected to rise, thereby exacerbating the decline in water quality correspondingly. This provides additional evidence for the hypothesis that population growth correlates positively with water quality degradation. In essence, as urban populations expand, there is an increasing concern regarding water quality; heightened human activity leads to greater discharge into the aquatic systems, complicating the management of household discharges and resulting in further deterioration of water quality.

In Nigeria, research conducted by (Ayobahan et al., 2015) identified various factors contributing to water quality variability at different sampling stations, including organic pollution, industrial effluent, soil erosion, nutrient loading, and human activities. The Water Quality Index (WQI) for sampling stations 1 and 3 was classified as very poor for drinking water (201 - 300), while stations 2, 4, and 5 were deemed unsuitable (> 301) for human consumption.

In the Limpopo province of South Africa, a study by (Edokpayi et al., 2018) surveyed 405

households in rural communities to assess water quality, focusing on water-use practices, perceptions regarding water quality, and household water-treatment methods. The study involved testing drinking water samples from households for microbiological contamination. In contrast, water from potential natural sources was evaluated for both physicochemical and microbiological quality during both the dry and wet seasons. The analysis of the results indicated that all tested natural water sources exhibited fecal contamination at various points in each season. Although the treated municipal supply did not show fecal contamination, it is noteworthy that this treated water system does not reach all residents in the valley, thereby creating a reliance on contaminated natural sources for some households. (Wang et al., 2021) investigated pollution sources in Weishan and Luoma Lakes. Their analysis revealed that the average levels of turbidity, total dissolved solids (TDS), total nitrogen (TN), total hardness (TH), and alkalinity (ALK) exceeded standard limits. While the CA results indicated varied sources and pathways for pollutants and ions, anthropogenic and industrial activities were the main contributors to water pollution in Weishan Lake. In contrast, Luoma Lake faced pollution primarily from anthropogenic, natural, and agricultural sources. The study further revealed that the main point sources of contaminant were coking, metal mining, and smelting industries.

Literature Review

The consumption of contaminated water poses significant threats to both human health and environmental integrity, affecting not only individuals but also agricultural activities and food security. Extensive research has documented the harmful effects of water pollution. For instance, Edokpayi pointed out that drinking microbially contaminated water can lead to serious health issues such as diarrheal diseases and enteropathy, primarily impacting children under five years old, who are especially vulnerable. In addition, Madhav et al. (2020) emphasized that pollutants in aquatic environments present a critical risk to human health and threaten the sustainability of aquatic ecosystems. Water pollutants can be categorized

into several types, including inorganic and organic pollutants, pathogens, thermal pollution, and radioactive substances. Each category contributes to the degradation of water quality, creating challenges for public health and environmental conservation. A study by Chen et al. (2019) showed there is a notable correlation between the estimated number of cancer cases and the reported incidence of cancers such as those of the pancreas, brain, leukemia, and thyroid in both men and women, along with colon, uterine corpus, and bladder cancers specifically affecting women.

Water quality issues are particularly pronounced in developing countries. Koukal et al. (2004) argue that nations with emerging economies do not allocate sufficient attention to contemporary environmental challenges when compared to developed countries, where pollution is systematically identified and addressed through the enactment of robust environmental legislation and the enforcement of regulations. Healey (2014) asserts that many developing countries lack adequate funding and the requisite human capital necessary to establish and maintain effective water quality monitoring programs, resulting in 80% of the continent's diseases attributable to poor water quality.

What is Water Quality

Water is categorized by source into two main types: groundwater and surface water. Based on quality, it can also be classified into four categories: potable, palatable, contaminated or polluted, and infected (Omer, 2019).

Regarding quality parameters, water is further divided into physical, chemical, and biological classifications (Touray & Zhou, 2024), (Omer, 2019), as seen in Table 1. Understanding the quality of drinking water is essential, as it directly affects its suitability for human consumption. The standards used to assess water quality are governed by regulations designed to ensure that drinking water meets specific criteria, thereby preventing health-related issues, the spread of diseases, technical disruptions, and aesthetic concerns (Touray & Zhou, 2024). The significance of water quality has increased due to the awareness that the quantity of water often cannot be evaluated in isolation from its quality.

Figure1. Classification of water based on its sources, quality, and parameters
 Source: The author

Figure 2. Water quality parameters adopted from
 Source: Omer, 2019

Water quality remains a critical factor in various sectors, including domestic use, agriculture, industrial water supply, fisheries, aquaculture production, aquatic recreation, and the overall health of ecosystems (Boyd, 2019). Water quality assesses how suitable water is for the needs of various biotic species and human purposes. (Omer, 2019). Water quality is a crucial factor in aligning water demand with supply. The acceptable criteria for water quality vary based on prevailing conditions and can change over time and across different regions. The water quality index significantly contributes to assessing the quality of a specific source, taking

into account both time and various influencing factors. Nonetheless, establishing a universally accepted water quality index proves to be quite challenging (Tirkey et al., 2013). Thus, to ensure that drinking and agricultural waters are safe, it is important to adhere to national and international water quality standards. (Kumar et al., 2024) emphasized that water quality is a crucial component in achieving sustainable development goals directly related to water, agriculture, biodiversity, health, and climate action, as it also plays a significant role in improving water quality and supplying clean water. The water quality index examines the vital

relationship between water supply and demand. Water Quality Indices (WQIs) have been used to measure water quality since the 1960s. They summarize water quality measurements into a single number categorized as poor, marginal, fair, excellent, and exceptional. WQIs provide a mechanism for tracking changes in water quality in response to specific needs and environmental challenges (Kumar et al., 2024).

Water Quality Regulations in the Gambia

In The Gambia, regulations governing the quality parameters of potable water are established and enforced by two primary institutions: the Food Safety and Quality Authority and the Public Utilities Regulatory Authority (Joof et al., 2024). The Department of Water Resources, situated within the Ministry of Fisheries and Water Resources, is responsible for conducting routine analyses of several water quality indicators. However, the frequency of these analyses is dependent on the availability of funding from the Public Utilities Regulatory Authority (PURA), which is often inconsistent. Furthermore, the data generated by these assessments is not disseminated publicly; instead, it remains internal and is archived (Conteh et al., 2020). The Gambia Standards Bureau plays a crucial role in developing standards that are mandatory and legally enforceable (Joof et al., 2024).

Water Pollution in the Gambia

The Gambia's water resources are predominantly derived from two primary sources: surface water and groundwater. Surface water encompasses the river systems, streams, and aquaculture ponds. In contrast, groundwater comprises supplies provided by the National Water and Electricity Company through piped water services, as well as private boreholes. Notably, private boreholes serve as a significant source of potable water in The Gambia (Conteh et al., 2020). However, these boreholes often lack regulation by the Department of Water Resources, leading to concerns regarding potential contamination (Boussouga et al., 2023). Furthermore, Conteh et al. (2020) note that the utilization of surface water for drinking purposes in The Gambia is infrequent, primarily attributable to the persistent salinity challenges

observed in the lower reaches of the River Gambia and its tributaries, where critical population centers and tourism amenities are situated. Water pollution in the Gambia has been attributed to solid waste disposal to water bodies, improper sewage management systems, oil spills, mining, floods, leachate percolation at dumpsites, and runoffs with contaminants dissolved or suspended in the water from dumpsites.

Solid Waste Disposal

According to the (WorldBank, 2021), 90% of waste in developing countries often ends up in open dumpsites or is openly incinerated, leading to catastrophic health and environmental issues. As the global population continues to grow, so does the accumulation of waste. Bakoteh dumpsite, for example, is Gambia's largest open dumpsite, covering a total area of about 17.8 hectares (Sanneh et al., 2011). This dumpsite serves as the final disposal site for residents under the Kanifing Municipal Council and other communities under the Brikama Area Council, making it the busiest open dumpsite in Gambia. As indicated by Sanneh et al. (2011), about 90% of the waste in Gambia is disposed of through open dumping without proper treatment.

Leachate Percolation

Open dump sites and improperly managed waste disposal systems remain major sources of leachate. Non-engineered landfill locations present significant environmental hazards, impacting air quality, biodiversity, soil health, and human well-being. Moreover, they pose considerable risks to groundwater resources (Srivastava et al., 2023). According to Sanneh et al. (2011), leachate typically contains high levels of organic carbon, ammonia, chloride, potassium, and hydrogen carbonate, which, once infiltrating the soil, can contaminate groundwater. Much of this organic matter resists biodegradation. Groundwater near the landfill is classified as non-potable and unsuitable for irrigation purposes (Fatta et al., 1999); (Mishra et al., 2019). The groundwater table in Gambia's largest open dumpsite is approximately 2 meters deep. Preliminary studies indicate significant fecal and coliform contamination in certain areas, rendering the water unsuitable for

domestic purposes. Water samples collected near the site reveal that 50% exhibit fecal coliform counts exceeding 100, with 93% showing total coliform counts greater than 100 per 100 mL. Despite these findings, many households in the vicinity continue to utilize this contaminated water for domestic activities, including bathing and washing (Sanneh et al., 2011).

Flooding

During the 1970s, drought in The Gambia caused several wetlands, including those around the Tanbi Wetland Park, Ebo Town, and Nema Kunku, to dry up for years (Kavegue & Eguavo, 2016). This time also saw significant urbanization, resulting in many people moving into these now-dry wetlands. Most of the areas occupied by these new settlers had previously served as natural waterways during the rainy seasons before the drought occurred. Given the ongoing rise in population and the related expansion of water and land use, the risk of contaminating aquatic ecosystems is increasing worldwide (Touray & Zhou, 2024). In urban areas, sewage infrastructure that incorporates waste stabilization ponds has been developed. These systems are designed to manage various diffuse sources that convey wastewater, ultimately discharging it 200 meters from the coastline into the ocean (Boussouga et al., 2023).

Figure 3. Flooding in The Gambia, late July 2022
Source: GambiaRedCrossSociety, 2022

However, during flood events such as the one illustrated in Figure 3, the sewage systems may become compromised, leading to the contamination of microbial colonies, specifically coliforms. This contamination typically arises from the presence of fecal matter or the infiltration of sewage effluent into the groundwater, rendering the water unfit for human consumption (Talha et al., 2019).

Mining

Mining serves as a profitable income source for both the Gambian government and individuals engaged in mining operations. While it has the potential to boost national and personal income, it also leads to significant environmental degradation and poses toxic hazards. According to Niane et al., artisanal small-scale gold mining (ASGM) has released considerable quantities of mercury (Hg) into the Gambia River ecosystem through the amalgamation processes. This mercury buildup in sediments poses serious health risks to humans and threats to aquatic life. Furthermore, in the Kedougou region of southeastern Senegal, through which the Gambia River flows before entering The Gambia, considerable contamination from mercury, chromium, copper, zinc, lead, and arsenic has been detected in river sediments, attributed to gold mining activities (Boussouga et al., 2023; Niane et al., 2014).

Pesticides and Pharmaceuticals

The street markets of The Gambia exhibit a substantial array of pesticides, encompassing up to 168 different components (Murphy et al., 2012). Among the most prevalent yet highly hazardous of these pesticides is 2,3-dichloro vinyl dimethyl phosphate, commercially known as SNIPER 1000EC. The government has initiated a ban on its use due to the detrimental effects it poses to water quality, environmental sustainability, and public health (Boussouga et al., 2023). Additionally, many of the pesticides available in The Gambia, including organophosphates, which constitute 38% of the local pesticide market, are either restricted or outright banned in numerous other countries (Boussouga et al., 2023). The prohibited pesticides are not permitted for application within the United States due to concerns

pertaining to public health and environmental integrity. These pesticides, alongside those identified as hazardous by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Prior Informed Consent (PIC) procedure, are deemed unsuitable for residential usage, as they present potential safety hazards for individuals and their families (Murphy et al., 2012). Furthermore, (Wilkinson et al., 2022) reported the presence of five active pharmaceutical ingredients (naproxen, clotrimazole, citalopram, paracetamol, and temazepam) detected in the Gambia River.

Materials and Methods

This research involves a comprehensive review of academic literature on water pollution in The Gambia. It specifically focuses on its effects on drinking and agricultural water while considering key terms such as water pollution, water quality, leachate percolation, drinking water, and irrigation water. Essential materials were obtained from reputable sources, including the Tonji University Online Library and journals such as Science Direct, PubMed, Scopus, and Springer, among others.

Study Area

The Gambia, situated in West Africa, stretches roughly 450 km along the River Gambia and encompasses an area of 10,689 km² (Bah et al., 2019). It is bordered by Senegal, except for a small 60 km² section along the western Atlantic Ocean, as illustrated in Figure 2. With a population of 2.4 million in 2020 and a density of 227 individuals per km² (GBoS, 2024), it ranks among the most densely populated nations in Africa (WorldBank, 2022). This high density places substantial pressure on arable land, adversely affecting the country's capacity to deliver social services (Sports, 2019). The Gambian economy is primarily agricultural but is significantly threatened by climate change, which brings increasing temperatures, declining rainfall, and rising sea levels. The region experiences a Sahelian climate characterized by an extended dry season from November to May and a short wet season from June to October. During the dry months, temperatures range from 18°C to 30°C, while the wet season sees temperatures fluctuating between 23°C and 33°C (Urquhart, 2016). Since 1960, the average

annual temperature has increased by 1.0°C, averaging an increase of 0.210°C per decade. The annual rainfall typically measures around 1,000 mm in the southern and southeastern areas, tapering to 700 mm in other parts (WorldBank, 2022).

The Gambia River, which bisects the country and discharges into the Atlantic Ocean, serves as a significant determinant in the topography of The Gambia. The majority of The Gambia's population is concentrated along the river, which facilitates the transportation of goods and serves as a vital resource for drinking and agricultural purposes (Healey, 2014). The Gambia River is recognized as a principal river in West Africa, covering approximately 12% of the nation's total land area (Boussouga et al., 2023). A significant proportion of Gambians (particularly in urban centers) rely on the national piped water supply managed by the National Water and Electricity Company, in addition to domestic boreholes that may pose contamination risks (Boussouga et al., 2023). In contrast to the national water supply, which undergoes routine disinfection. The Gambia has made notable strides in enhancing the quality of potable water, increasing access from 86% in 2010 to 90% in 2018. However, it is reported by (Unicef, 2020) that only 34% of households utilize safely managed drinking water services.

Figure 4. Bakoteh Dumpsite
Source: Holloway, 2019

Indiscriminate solid waste dumping is a key cause of pollution affecting both surface and

groundwater, jeopardizing drinking water quality for nearby residents. The Bakoteh dumpsite, the largest in The Gambia, serves as the main disposal site for the Kanifing Municipal Council and surrounding communities, making it the most visited dumpsite in the country.

The site was originally a stone quarry, but for the past three decades, both the Municipal Council and informal sectors have indiscriminately disposed of waste at this location. Initially isolated, the site has, over time, become engulfed within a densely populated community due to factors such as population growth, urbanization, and housing demands. As the population in urban Gambia increases, so too does the volume of municipal solid waste (MSW) disposed of at this dumpsite. The accumulation of waste without proper treatment poses severe health and environmental risks to residents living in the vicinity. With the ongoing challenges posed by urbanization, population growth, and increasing reliance on a singular water supply source (national piped water), the provision of safe and clean drinking water continues to be a pressing challenge for The Gambia.

Results

The majority of the Gambian population resides in urban areas, contributing to urban Gambia's status as one of the most densely populated regions in Africa. This urban populace relies heavily on government provisions for access to water for daily consumption. However, the escalating trends of population growth and urbanization have adverse effects on both surface and groundwater quality. These effects are largely attributable to human encroachment and the resulting contamination of these vital water sources. The Gambia River, along with rainwater and boreholes, serves as a primary resource for agricultural practices in The Gambia. A significant portion of the Gambian population relies on borehole water provided by the National Water and Electricity Company, particularly in urban centers. Additionally, many households depend on domestic boreholes, which pose potential contamination risks, as previously discussed. In contrast, the national

water supply undergoes routine disinfection processes.

The increasing reliance on borehole water can be attributed to the salinization and contamination of surface waters, which has rendered boreholes the principal source of drinking water, followed closely by bottled water (Kral et al., 2019). The quality of water, both for drinking and agricultural purposes, has been adversely affected by various anthropogenic activities. These include domestic practices such as bathing, washing, and the improper disposal of municipal waste, alongside agricultural activities characterized by excessive pesticide use and industrial waste discharge. Despite notable progress in enhancing the quality of potable water—rising from 86% coverage in 2010 to 90% in 2018—only 34% of households utilize safely managed drinking water services, as reported by UNICEF (2020). There remains a significant gap in available data regarding the current status of both groundwater and surface water quality in The Gambia (Healey, 2014). However, recent research conducted by Boussouga et al. (2023) suggests that the Gambia River may be deemed suitable for drinking water after appropriate treatment measures are implemented.

Discussion

The impact of water pollution on human health is considerable, with variations that can depend on factors such as region, age, and gender. Diarrhea is the most prevalent disease linked to water pollution, primarily transmitted by enteroviruses in aquatic environments (Lin et al., 2022). Both acute and chronic health risks have been identified for certain commonly detected pesticides at their highest concentrations. Epidemiological studies conducted in Ethiopia have also shown that exposure to pesticides is associated with acute poisoning, respiratory issues, neurobehavioral symptoms, and breast cancer (Asefa et al., 2024). Children are particularly vulnerable to the negative impacts of water pollution. Research conducted by (Lin et al., 2022) highlights that diarrhea remains a predominant cause of morbidity and mortality among young children in low-income countries.

Malaria, RDT positive cases, all districts

Cases of diarrhea with blood (DWB)

Figure 5. United Nations Disaster Assessment and Coordination
Source: UNDAC

Figure 5 presented above indicates that by July 2022, a period during which The Gambia experienced its most severe flooding in approximately fifty years, there was a notable increase in the rates of confirmed cases of malaria and diarrhea. The rapid escalation in the incidence of these two significant public health challenges can be attributed to the contamination of local water resources, which has exacerbated the prevalence of these waterborne diseases. It is well-established that physical illness can adversely affect cognitive functioning; thus, students who suffer from waterborne diseases due to consumption of contaminated water are likely to experience considerable school absenteeism. This condition may lead to detrimental consequences on their overall academic performance. In response to the threat of floods and associated illnesses, residents of Ebo Town have implemented

measures to limit school attendance to safeguard their children (Kavegue & Eguavo, 2016). Consumption of contaminated water can result in various health complications, necessitating medical intervention that incurs financial burdens, including hospital expenses, pharmaceutical costs, transportation fees, and other related expenditures for individuals. Furthermore, the adverse impact of polluted water on livestock and crops can lead to significant economic losses for farmers due to diminished productivity and increased mortality rates among animals. In the long term, the costs associated with the remediation of contaminated water sources are consistently substantial.

Conclusion

Polluted water contaminated with hazardous chemicals poses significant risks to human health, agricultural productivity, and the integrity

of the land utilized for crop cultivation. Anthropogenic activities are a major determinant of water pollution. The floods of 2022, as previously discussed, have precipitated a critical public health crisis, particularly evident in the increased incidence of malaria and diarrhea. It is evident that human interventions, including deforestation, mining, and suboptimal agricultural practices, have exacerbated the severity of these floods. Furthermore, the prevailing attitudes of certain individuals towards waste management practices have negatively impacted water quality. Therefore, it is imperative for the Gambian government to consider the establishment of an ultra-filtration plant in proximity to the freshwater regions of the River Gambia to enhance access to safe and high-quality drinking water. This initiative could significantly mitigate the pressure on drinking water supplies in the provinces. In addition, routine monitoring and maintenance of both national and individual borehole water systems, along with the enhancement of existing sanitation infrastructure, are vital. Increased budget allocation for water quality control and management is essential, as is the transition towards sustainable agricultural practices, the implementation of a circular economy in waste management, and the promotion of balanced mining operations.

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